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ТРУДНОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА, ВЫЗВАННЫЕ ГРАММАТИЧЕСКИМИ ОСОБЕННОСТЯМИ АНГЛИЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

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TRANSLATION DIFFICULTIES CAUSED BY GRAMMATICAL FEATURES OF THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

Аннотация:

Язык, как известно, является важнейшим средством человеческого общения, с помощью которого люди обмениваются мыслями и достигают взаимопонимания. Общение между людьми с помощью языка осуществляется двумя способами: устно и письменно. Если коммуниканты говорят на одном языке, то общение происходит непосредственно, однако, когда люди говорят на разных языках, непосредственное общение становится невозможным. В этом случае на помощь приходит перевод, который многие исследователи определяют как передачу мыслей, выраженных на другом языке, средствами одного языка. Перевод, таким образом, является важным вспомогательным средством, обеспечивающим выполнение языком его коммуникативной функции, когда люди выражают свои мысли на разных языках. Перевод играет большую роль в обмене мыслями между разными народами и служит делу распространения сокровищ мировой культуры.

Abstract:

Language, as is known, is the most important means of human communication, with the help of which people exchange thoughts and achieve mutual understanding. Communication between people using language is carried out in two ways: orally and in writing. If the communicators speak the same language, then communication occurs directly, however, when people speak different languages, direct communication becomes impossible. In this case, translation comes to the rescue, which many researchers define as the transmission of thoughts expressed in another language by means of one language. Translation is therefore an important auxiliary tool that ensures that language fulfills its communicative function when people express their thoughts in different languages. Translation plays a major role in the exchange of thoughts between different peoples and serves the cause of disseminating the treasures of world culture.

Ключевые слова: разные языки, особенности перевода, трудности перевода, грамматические особенности, теория перевода

Key word: different languages, features of translation, translation difficulties, grammatical features, theory of translation

In our article we will consider written literary translation, in which the translator's tasks become more complex, since in addition to conveying the content, the translator must strive to preserve the form and style of the original (as much as possible).

This work is devoted to the grammatical difficulties of translating a literary text from English into Azerbaijani. In order to clarify the nature of such difficulties, an attempt will be made to analyze the systemic differences between the two languages and the methods of grammatical consolidation of the logic of thinking in statements.

This article will examine the ways in which professional translators overcome grammatical difficulties and achieve adequate translation. We will use examples from the works of the famous English writer W.S.

Maugham, whose style has been admired by many literary figures.

This, in turn, requires elucidation of the problem of translation adequacy. Is it possible to convey in one language thoughts expressed by means of another language with complete accuracy and completeness? On this issue, two opposing points of view have developed in the scientific community.

1. "The Theory of Untranslatability". According to this theory, a full translation from one language to another is generally impossible due to the significant divergence of the expressive means of different languages; a translation is only a weak and imperfect reflection of the original, giving a very vague idea of it.[1]

2. Another point of view, which is held by the majority of researchers, including L.S. Barkhudarov and A.V. Fedorov, and which underlies the work of many professional translators, is that any developed national language is a completely sufficient means of communication for the full transfer of thoughts expressed in another language. This is especially true for the Azerbaijani language - one of the most developed and rich languages in the world. The practice of translators proves that any work can be fully (adequately) translated into Azerbaijani while preserving all the stylistic and other features inherent in a given author.

In his article "The Mastery of Literary Translation" A.A. Smirnov says that the task of an adequate literary translation is considered to be the transfer of the meaning of the content, emotional expressiveness and verbal-structural design of the original. Adequate, from the point of view of A.A. Smirnov, we should recognize "a translation in which all the author's intentions (both thought out by him and unconscious) are conveyed in the sense of a certain ideological-emotional impact on the reader, with observance, as far as possible (by selecting exact equivalents) of all the resources of imagery, color, rhythm and so on used by the author; the latter should be considered, however, not as an end in itself, but only as a means to achieve the general effect. Undoubtedly, in this case, it is necessary to sacrifice something, choosing less essential moments of the text".[2]

From this we can conclude that a translation that is adequate in artistic terms may not be adequate in linguistic terms.

According to G. Gachechiladze, literary translation in most cases fluctuates between two extreme principles: a literally accurate, but artistically incomplete translation and an artistically complete, but far from the original, free translation. These two principles are reflected in two main points of view: the definition of translation from the linguistic and literary positions. The linguistic principle of translation primarily assumes the recreation of the formal structure of the original. G. Gachechiladze believes that literary translation should be considered as a type of word-creating art, that is, not from a linguistic, but from a literary point of view. According to this theory, the main driving force of the translator should be the idea inspired by the original, which forces him to look for adequate linguistic means to reflect the thought in words, that is, a literary translation is an adequate correspondence to the original not in a linguistic, but in an aesthetic sense.

English and Azerbaijani are examples of two types of languages: analytical and synthetic. The very name of these types of languages shows that they are essentially different, in their principle of construction, and even opposite. However, this opposition is formal, since it concerns the expression of the same content. Understanding and mastering precisely this formal, specific, qualitative side, comparing the systemic features of the source language and the target language is necessary for adequate translation.[3]

Many modern linguists (Apollova M.A., Sternin I.A., Avrorin V.A.) proceed from the position that in languages with an analytical structure the logic of

thinking receives the clearest external and grammatical consolidation, dismembered in its elements, while in synthetic languages this logic acts rather as an internal relation in the assumption, an internal connection in the word. According to M.A. Apollova, "when we correlate the structure of language with the logic of thinking, we approach linguistic phenomena in their connection and integrity, in other words, from the side of syntax." At the same time, such scientists as T.N. Mikhelson, N.V. Uspenskaya, T.N. Malchevskaya, who are known for developing practical manuals for translating literature of various genres, highlight individual sections of grammar in their works (for example, infinitive phrases, passive voice), leaving small sections for describing syntactic difficulties (translating substitute words or some conjunctions).[4]

In order to consider the grammatical difficulties of translation and to clarify the nature of the differences in the expression of the same plan of content in the FL and TL, it is necessary to consider the structural and semantic relations within a sentence (utterance), since "a judgment, a form of thought is reflected in the logical structure of a sentence, and their construction reflects the relationship between objects, their properties and qualities." "We most directly encounter the expression of the logic of thinking in the grammatical form of analytical languages, for it is clear that the direct word order in a sentence coincides with the sequence of logical components (subject - predicate - object)." Violation of the direct word order in a narrative sentence in English looks like something unusual, like an expressive stylistic device. Consequently, in English one can observe the most complete correspondence of logical components and syntactic forms. In synthetic languages, to which Russian belongs, the concrete meaning of a word, semantic stress dominates over formal syntactic moments, which leads to much greater external freedom of syntactic constructions and to an almost complete absence of formal fixation of the place of a word in a sentence. In other words, languages of an analytical structure rely mainly on inflections.[5]

As already noted, the translation must fully satisfy the generally accepted norms of the Azerbaijani literary language. Each phrase must sound lively and natural, without retaining any hints of syntactic constructions of the original that are alien to the Azerbaijani language. In view of the significant discrepancy in the syntactic structure of the English and Azerbaijani languages, as noted above, it is rarely possible to preserve the form of expression of the original in translation. Moreover, in the interests of the accuracy of conveying the meaning, it is often necessary to resort to changing the structure of the translated sentence in accordance with the norms of the Azerbaijani language, i.e. to rearrange or even completely replace individual words and expressions, although the replacement of even one word with another is very significant. [6] In translation, not one, but all words are replaced by others, which, among other things, belong to a different language system, which is distinguished by its own special speech structure - the order of words in a sentence, words belonging to the same synonymous series, as a rule, differ significantly in semantic shades in different languages

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